

EFFECT OF HIGH TEMPERATURE ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF A PLAIN WEAVE CFRP LAMINATE UNDER TENSION-TENSION LOADING

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ABSTRACT

This study is focused on the experimental characterization of the effect of a high temperature on the fatigue behavior of a plain weave CFRP laminate. Specifically, the delamination onset and propagation in the vicinity of a pre-existing flaw is investigated. Specimens made of plain weave carbon/epoxy prepreg material and were tested under tension-tension fatigue loading at 7 Hz ($R = 0.1$). All the experiments were carried out at 250°F, corresponding to high temperature dry (HTD) environmental conditions. Embedded in the specimens was a Teflon insert acting as an artificial flaw. The surface strain near the artificial flaw was measured using an in-house developed high-speed video extensometer, allowing tracking the increase of the displacement during fatigue tests. Based on the author's previous work [9] it was assumed that the increase of the displacement might be related to the initiation and progression of the delamination in the specimens. The S-N curve at delamination onset was established for the plain weave CFRP at HTD and it was compared to the curve obtained at room temperature dry (RTD). It is clear from the curve that a hot environment has a detrimental effect on the delamination resistance in fatigue. The damage modes at different number of cycles and load levels were investigated using C-Scan imaging and optical microscopy. The equations of the S-N curves could then be used as preliminary tools for the design of structures involving plain weave CFRPs. In addition, it was observed that the criterion for the detection of the delamination onset based on the increase of the displacement was different at HTD (5% increase) and at RTD (10% increase). Future work will be focused on the testing of additional environmental conditions, such as intermediate temperature (180°F) and high humidity level (95% RH).

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite materials are used extensively in aerospace structures because of their high stiffness-to-weight ratio. These structures typically are exposed to a wide range of environmental conditions, including cold and hot temperatures as well as low and high humidity levels. Laminates based on plain weave fabric reinforcement present some advantageous characteristics when compared to unidirectional laminates, such as better drapeability and resistance to delamination. However, the literature dealing with the fatigue behaviour of plain weave fabrics is limited, especially if the composite contains an embedded flaw (delamination). It is now established that both the mechanical properties and the damage modes can be affected by the phenomenon of fatigue and by the environmental conditions. Therefore it is of primary importance for the aerospace industry to acquire more knowledge on the mechanical response of composites under different fatigue loading modes and environmental conditions.

In order to study the fatigue behaviour of the composite, the determination of a fatigue delamination onset criterion is required. Hwang and Han successfully introduced a strain failure criterion to study the fatigue behaviour of glass fibre reinforced epoxy composite materials [1].

Several authors considered the critical condition for predicting fatigue life to occur at a definite percentage of stiffness loss (3%, 5%, 10% and 20%) [2-8].

This paper is focused on the experimental characterization of the effect of a high temperature on the fatigue behaviour of a plain weave carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminate with an embedded flaw under constant amplitude cyclic tensile loading. This report also includes the identification of the delamination onset fatigue criterion at high temperature.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Specimens were manufactured from plain weave carbon fibre fabric/epoxy prepreg material. A stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_s$ was selected. Two layers of Teflon foil sealed by an adhesive were embedded at the center of the specimens, between the 3rd and 4th plies from top of the laminate, in order to create an artificial flaw. This location was identified as a delamination-prone interface because of the mismatch of the mechanical properties of the plies located above and below the flaw. The specimen geometry is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Specimen dimensions with embedded flaw

Mechanical tests were carried out using an MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine. Aluminum end tabs and stainless steel woven wire mesh were used between the specimen and the hydraulic wedge grips to prevent slippage during loading. An atmospheric chamber was used to maintain the desired temperature throughout the test. Quasi-static tensile tests were conducted on five specimens containing an artificial flaw. The tests were performed at 250°F, corresponding to high temperature dry (HTD) environmental condition. Every test was started after the specimen reached equilibrium at HTD. Each specimen was loaded to failure under displacement control at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. The mean of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) was calculated based on the maximum load recorded during the test and the cross-section area of the specimens.

Load-controlled tension-tension fatigue tests at HTD were performed at a load ratio $R = 0.1$ and a frequency $f = 7$ Hz. The fatigue tests were conducted at various percentages of the UTS, i.e. 60%, 55% and 50% of UTS. Three specimens were used for each load level.

Figure 2 – Mechanical testing set-up : (a) Equipment,
(b) Reference dots on specimen for image correlation software

As in the author's previous work [9], the strain field on the surface of the specimen was monitored using an in-house developed video extensometer system, in order to assess damage progression (Figure 2a). Eleven 3 mm-diameter reference dots (stickers) were placed on the surface of the specimen following the pattern illustrated in Figure 4b. The dots "1" and "2" were used to calculate the overall longitudinal strain of the specimen in real time, so that the test could be stopped when the stiffness loss criterion was reached. The remaining dots were placed near and around the inserted flaw for tracking the local strain field. The local strain field was used as an indicator of the delamination onset.

An ultrasonic immersion scanner (TecScan with the TecView™ UT software) was used to inspect the specimens prior and after testing. A focal ultrasonic transducer (V309 Panametric, 5 MHz, 12.7 mm in diameter, 50.8 mm PTF) was used and the C-Scan capability of the software allowed the detection of the delamination propagation.

The results of the C-scan analysis were validated by optical microscopy for specimens tested at 70°F which corresponds to room temperature dry (RTD) condition [9]. Figure 3 shows typical damage found around the flaw and the position of that damage on a c-scan analysis.

Figure 3 - C-scan and optical micrograph of the same specimen; (a) C-scan of RTD specimen fatigued to 10% increase of longitudinal strain, square shape shows position of flaw, arrow shows approximate position of micrograph, (b) Typical damage found around the flaw, optical micrograph made with NMM-8TRF type optical microscope at 50X.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quasi-static results

An example of normalized quasi-static load-displacement curves of specimens tested at RTD and HTD is presented in Figure 4. The values are normalized to the average load and displacement at failure for each specimen. According to this figure, it is clear that both the stress and strain at failure are lower for the specimens tested at HTD compared to those tested at RTD condition. Indeed the average load and displacement at failure at HTD are 8.8% lower than those at RTD. Moreover the apparent stiffness of the specimens was reduced under the high temperature condition (2% lower).

Figure 4 - Normalized stress-strain curves of quasi-static tensile tests at RTD and HTD

The failure modes at HTD were investigated and compared to the failure modes observed at RTD. Examples of different types of failure as obtained in a previous study are presented in Figure 5a [9], while Figure 5b shows the broken specimens from the present study. In this figure it can be seen that the final failure of the specimens did not always occur at the inserted flaw, for both temperatures. Therefore it can be stated that the temperature did not have any significant effect on the failure mode of the specimens in their present configuration, under quasi-static loading.

Figure 5 - Fracture modes of specimens tested to failure under static tensile loading:
(a) RTD, (b) HTD

Fatigue results

The fatigue delamination onset criterion was determined from the increase of the longitudinal strain, in percent, defined as:

$$\% \text{ Strain Increase} = \frac{\epsilon_N - \epsilon_{1000}}{\epsilon_{1000}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{1000} and ϵ_N are the longitudinal strains at 1000 and N loading cycles, respectively, measured at the peak of the loading cycle, i.e., at maximum load.

In order to determine the appropriate criterion for the delamination onset at the inserted flaw, fatigue tests were conducted on three specimens at 60% of UTS at HTD. The tests were stopped at three distinct delamination onset criteria: 5%, 7% and 10%. To detect the delamination propagation in the specimens, inspections were made using C-Scan imaging before and after the fatigue tests.

C-Scan images of two different specimens tested in fatigue up to 5% and 7% of longitudinal strain increase are shown on Figure 6. The size of the Teflon insert is represented by the square shape in this figure. The propagation of delamination around the inserted flaw was obvious for the specimen fatigued up to 7% of longitudinal strain increase (Figure 6b). The specimen tested up to 5% of longitudinal strain increase (Figure 6a) showed the beginning of the delamination propagation. Since a 5% of strain increase corresponded to the onset of the delamination propagation, it was selected as the onset criterion for the fatigue tests at HTD.

Figure 6 – Ultrasonic C-scan images around back surface of specimens showing delamination propagation at HTD, square shape shows approximate position of flaw: (a) specimen fatigued to 5% increase of longitudinal strain, (b) specimen fatigued to 7% increase of longitudinal strain

The normalized S–N curves obtained from the fatigue tests at HTD and RTD [9] are shown on Figure 6. A linear regression was conducted for both testing conditions. It should be noted that both regression curves are log-based curves. The numerical expression for the curves is:

$$\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{UTS}} = A \ln(N_{onset}) + B \quad (2)$$

where σ_{max} is the maximum applied stress, σ_{UTS} is the UTS, A is the slope of the logarithmic function and N_{onset} is the number of cycles needed to reach the delamination onset criterion as defined previously (5% increase of the longitudinal strain). The value of parameters A and B were estimated to be -0.057 and 1.3278 respectively at RTD [9] and -0.022 and 0.8055 at HTD.

An equation was developed to predict the number of cycles at delamination onset between 70°F and 250°F. The assumptions used are that (a) the curves are both log-based, (b) the curves intersect at some point, and (c) the effect of temperature is linear between the two conditions. The equation is as follows:

$$N_{onset} = e^{\left[\frac{\sigma_{normal} - 0.48 + 14.92\alpha}{\alpha} \right]} \quad (3)$$

where N_{onset} is the number of cycles needed for delamination onset, σ_{normal} is the normalized stress and α is defined as:

$$\alpha = -0.057 + 1.94 \times 10^{-4}(T - 70) \quad (4)$$

where T is the temperature in °F.

Figure 7 - Normalized S-N curves for the carbon fibre/epoxy specimens containing an artificial flaw at RTD and HTD. The x-axis corresponds to the number of cycles required to reach the delamination onset criterion

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper experimental tests were carried out on a CFRP composite laminate made of plain weave fabric prepreg material with the aim of better understanding the fatigue behaviour of this material at high temperature. More precisely, the relation between the fatigue life up to a failure criterion of the laminate at RTD and HTD with the presence of a delamination in the laminate was assessed. A failure criterion was also proposed for detecting delamination onset in fatigue.

From the proposed results and discussion, some considerations can be summarized in conclusion:

- The static tensile properties were affected by a high test temperature;
- The onset criterion under HTD condition was determined to be $\Delta\varepsilon_{onset-HTD} = 5\%$. The measurements were made possible by the use of an in-house designed high-speed video extensometer;
- The S-N curve corresponding to the delamination onset under HTD condition was established allowing us to determine a mathematical relation of the fatigue life of the specimen at HTD and RTD.

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